

A TOOL FOR INTERFACING INJECTION CONDITIONS AND STRESS ANALYSIS FOR SFR THERMOPLASTIC PARTS

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ABSTRACT: This work concerns the high pressure injection of semi structural polymer -short fiber reinforced- parts. The Academia-Industry collaboration involves three aeronautical companies from Toulouse (Liebherr Aerospace, Microturbo and Technofan of the Snecma group) and two academic laboratories of the French Midi-Pyrenees region (the Research Center on "Tools, Materials and Processes" of the School Engineering of Mines of Albi Carmaux and the research team "Processes and Mechanical Properties of Composite structures" of the Mechanical Engineering Laboratory of Toulouse). It deals with the global problems from the manufacturing process to the structural analysis of injected parts: the body of an aircraft pressure valve, a first stage stator with an assembly of composite blades and a fan wheel). Although the aeronautical requirements have to be respected, the project is not reduced to a simple substitution of metallic materials by advanced technical materials but involves a new design of the part. The main part of this work is the interfacing of the industrial computational tools for fiber orientation with the mechanical response of structures. The mathematical representation of the fiber orientation follows Advani's method. It is integrated within the calculation methods of the mechanical properties, based on homogenization techniques. From a practical point of view, this interface allows the results of a numerical injection simulation to be obtained in terms of fiber orientation data (components of the Advani's tensor), one finite element after the other and throughout the thickness of the piece. An estimation of the homogenized mechanical properties is carried out locally based on the Mori and Tanaka method. The interface then builds the numerical pattern in relation to a code by associating the calculated local properties with the finite elements and a chosen mesh (from the same CAD pattern for the two analysis types). The corresponding results obtained at the various stages of the interface program execution are available for the design department engineer in order to check their relevance.

KEYWORD: industrial applications, integrated design and manufacturing, SFR thermoplastic injection, stress analysis, composite structures.

INTRODUCTION

The dimensioning of a short fiber reinforced thermoplastic structure lies within the scope of a global methodology which relates the jobs of the plasturgist and the mechanical engineer. The plasturgist is concerned with design of the tools and the mechanical engineer with the structure. The position of fibers in all points of the part constitutes their common denominator. It influences both the dimensional accuracy of the finished part (withdrawals) and its mechanical resistance in service. As figure 1 indicates, the reinforcement position is influenced by the flow of filled polymer. The shape of the part and the anisotropic viscosity of filled polymer, influence the various modes of material flow. This form is obviously directly related to the tools. The dimensioning of the structure integrates the various scales of the part: total (form) and local (orientation of the reinforcements).

Figure 1: Methodology for the dimensioning of reinforced thermoplastic structures with short fibers.

The work to be carried out is placed within the framework of an integrated approach of dimensioning illustrated by figure 2. The essential part relates to the interfacing of the industrial computational tools for orientation of fibers with flow and mechanical response of structures. The codes of simulation of the conditions of injection use the mathematical representation of the orientation of fibers proposed by Advani [1]. This is integrated within the methods of calculation of the mechanical properties, based on a method of homogenization.

Figure 2: Integrated approach of dimensioning (MTD interface).

From a practical point of view, this interface (called by its author, E Haramburu, M.T.D.: Mori-Tanaka-DOS) makes it possible to recover the results of a numerical calculation of injection in terms of fiber orientation (components of the tensor of Advani), element by element and in the thickness of the part. It should be noted that taking into account the orientation data via the representation of Advani is unavoidable in the integrated approach (result of injection calculations). A calculation of the homogenized mechanical properties is carried out locally using the method of Mori and Tanaka [2]. The interface then builds the numerical model by a dialogue with a computer code of structure while associating with the finite elements and a mesh the calculated local properties (starting from the same model CAD for the two types of calculation). The results corresponding to the various stages carried out by the program of interface are at the disposal of the design office engineer in order to control their relevance. The interface is currently used in the design offices of the industrial partners [3].

REPRESENTATION OF HETEROGENEITIES AND HOMOGENISATION OF A THERMOPLASTIC INJECTED WITH SHORT FIBRES

A fiber is represented by a field of ellipsoidal form embedded in the polymeric matrix already disturbed by the presence of other heterogeneities (method of Mori-Tanaka). In fact, it is a family of reinforcements having identical characteristics (elastic properties, form, orientation ...). The influence of the conditions of flow leads to a heterogeneity of orientation described by the tensor of Advani whose components correspond to projections of the function of distribution of orientation of fibers. The physical direction of the components of the tensor of orientation is associated, for the diagonal components, with the probability of presence of a volumic fraction of heterogeneities. The use of second-order tensors consists in a simplified representation of the orientation, i.e. to a loss of information on the real distribution of the orientation of the groups of fibers. This type of representation is imposed by calculations of injection of charged polymer. The calculation on average of equivalent homogeneous material is associated with the probability of presence of a group of

fibers, while placing itself in the principal reference mark of the tensor of Advani. In this configuration, the physical interpretation of its components is direct (probabilities of orientation of the respective groups of fibers). Consequently knowing the probabilities of orientation in the principal reference mark of the tensor of Advani, one is able to give a representation of the composite with short fibers within the meaning of the methods of homogenization. Elementary Volume Representative of material consists of four phases: the polymeric matrix and three (3D) or two (2D) heterogeneities or "families" of orientation. The orientations are the three principal directions. The associated probabilities of presence are the eigenvalues of the tensor of Advani. The volumic fractions according to principal directions are obtained by multiplying the respective probabilities of presence by the total percentage of reinforcements. The homogenization step is presented in simplified way for a 2D case in figure 3.

Mori and Tanaka's method: stiffness matrix of the equivalent homogeneous composite material in (I, II) then (1,2)

Figure 3: Homogenization step (C^R and C^M mechanical characteristics of the reinforcements and the matrix; aspect ratio of the reinforcement $R = \text{length/diameter}$).

DISCUSSION OF THE MICROMECHANICAL MODEL

The method of homogenization used is traditional [4], but has the effect of integrating a tensor of Advani for data of orientation. An evaluation of the micromechanical model was carried out [5]. Simplified representations of composite material with short fibers were considered. The results presented make it possible to highlight certain problems associated with the use of the Advani tensor to represent a reinforced short fiber material. The results of a calculation of homogenization of a material with unidirectional reinforcements are proposed. In this case, the probability of the orientation of the reinforcements according to the direction "L" (direction fiber) is represented by the tensor of components $a_{LL} = 1$ and $a_{ij} = 0 \forall i, j \neq L$. The calculation of modulus E_L is particularly sensitive to the value of the aspect ratio R in a range of values lower than 20. In the case of injected polymeric materials, R is between 1 and 30 for a diameter of glass fiber of about $10 \mu\text{m}$ [6]. The increase in the Young's modulus E_L per unit of aspect ratio is higher than 700 MPa for a value of R of about 5. It is lower than 200 MPa when R is higher than 20. The conditions of injection can have an influence on the values of R . The plasticization of the material (malaxation in the screw of injection) is the most damaging phase of the production cycle for the length of the reinforcement. It is thus necessary to avoid carrying out an evaluation of R from granulated raw material (before the beginning of the cycle of injection). The average length of fibers contained in the raw material pellets is of the order $170 \mu\text{m}$ and is only $130 \mu\text{m}$ in the finished part. Then results of a study of the behavior of a

composite with a bidirectional orientation distribution known as "balanced" are given. It presents the same proportion of reinforcements in two directions noted 1 and 2. For this state of orientation, the only non zero components of the Advani tensor are a_{11} and a_{22} equal to 0.5. These components correspond to an infinity of orientation distributions, of which the particular case of composite material with reinforcements distributed uniformly in all the directions of the plan (1, 2). The representation of Advani thus does not make it possible to distinguish between these two situations of orientation. In this context, it is thus necessary to be careful in the stage of representation of material. By way of comparison, a calculation of homogenization was carried out by representing isotropic material with 20 phases of heterogeneity [5]. They are regularly distributed between 0 and 360° and their volumic fractions correspond to one 20th of the total volumic fraction. Each phase is located by the polar angle. It is defined between direction 1 and one unspecified direction X of the plane (1, 2) such that $a_{xx} = 1$, $a_{yy} = a_{33} = 0$ and $a_{ij} = 0$ if $i \neq j$ with (X, Y, 3) local basis. The evolution of the technical moduli according to the orientation is calculated for Poisson ratios of the matrix and the reinforcements respectively equal to $\nu_M = 0.35$ and $\nu_F = 0.25$, and for a ratio E_F / E_M of the Young's moduli of the reinforcements and matrix equal to 20. The total volumic fraction F and the aspect ratio R are respectively equal to 0.2 and 15. When orientation varies from 0 to 360°, the evolution of ratio E_X / E_M is given in figure 4 for composite materials respectively isotropic and "well balanced".

Figure 4: Reduced moduli E_X^0 of traction according to direction X for composite materials respectively, isotropic and "well balanced".

"MORI-TANAKA-DOS" INTERFACE

The interface "Mori-Tanaka-DOS" (MTD) is a program which is coded in FORTRAN 77. This choice guarantees a relative portability of MTD since the source code can be compiled under various environments such as MS-DOS or UNIX. The structure of MTD is organized in the form of various blocks of routines representing more than 10000 lines of code. The core of the calculation of the interface is dedicated in particular to the estimate of the homogenized elastic properties. This block represents only one tenth of the volume of MTD. The remainder deals with the management of the entries of the program and the postprocessing placed at the disposal of the user. The link between the tools for simulation of injection and computer codes of structure is based on the possibility of reading the data coming from simulation of injection and of writing the elastic properties in a format accessible by a computer code of structure.

It is possible to work with two models relatively independent for calculations of injection and structure, thanks to the juxtaposition of properties between meshes. The functions of the MTD interface allow to:

- read the data coming from injection simulation (characteristics of the mesh and data of orientation on the elements) and data processing of orientation for calculation of the elastic properties,
- write the elastic properties to the format of a "target" computer code,
- calculate of the elastic properties independently of the format of the data coming from the computational tools "upstream" and "downstream",
- friendly use for design offices through graphic interfaces,
- have independence of meshes of the injection simulation and the structural analysis,
- be free of reading or writing data from or towards any computer code (reception or preparation of data-processing data according to various formats).

It is noted that, whatever the format, the input/output data and of exit are always: the Advani tensor, elastic moduli, and characteristics of meshes. With the output of the resolution of the equations of flow and orientation, the presence of fibers is known in the form of one or more Advani tensors on each finite element of the mesh of the simulation of injection. In order to handle these sizes, the characteristics of the mesh (like the co-ordinates of the nodes and the tables of connection of the elements) are also data of the calculation of orientation. The juxtaposition of properties between the meshes of injection and structural analysis leads to the possibility to treat all the links of the integrated approach of mechanical dimensioning [7].

1. Juxtaposition of properties

The principle of juxtaposition is based on a criterion of proximity between the barycentres of the finite elements of a mesh (called "source" mesh) on which properties are affected and those of a mesh (called "target" mesh) on which they are required. From the co-ordinates of the nodes and the tables of connectivity of the elements of the two meshes, the co-ordinates of the barycentres of all the elements are calculated. The distance between the barycentres is then a particular size as it is single information available to appreciate the relevance of the juxtaposition. One can stress that the type of juxtaposed properties is unspecified since, for an element of the target mesh, it is the link with an element of the source mesh which is required. One has two sets of geometrical points. "Target" points are more or less close to "source" points. Thus with the criterion of proximity, the point source closest to each target point is required. This criterion makes sense only if the two meshes (injection and structural analysis) were created starting from same CAD model of the part studied or if they are geometrically superimposable. When the source point is found, the link is too. One follows the number of the "source" element which makes it possible to juxtapose the "source" property (of unspecified nature) on the "target" element.

With the MTD interface, the juxtaposition of properties between meshes applies more particularly to the orientation data in the form of Advani tensors. It should be noted that it is more practical to handle tensors of the second order with 5 independent components (because of the symmetry of the tensor and the condition of standardization on the diagonal components) than tensors of rigidity of order 4 (law of Hooke). The conditions of injection can be represented only on the complete part. The structural analysis does not have this type of constraint. This function of the interface is useful if the study of the mechanical response relates to only one portion of a part.

2. Simulation of the conditions of injection

For the simulation of the conditions of injection, two options are available with the code used (Moldflow): the injection known as "Double Skin" (DP) and the injection known as "Average Skin" (PM). In the case of injection DP, the digital model is a mesh of surfaces limiting the volume of the studied part (skin of the part) made of elements without thickness. For injection PM, the mesh of the part is a surface model corresponding, in the majority of the cases, in the average plane of the part. Generally, injection PM is easiest to implement while being sufficiently representative of the geometry of the part. On the other hand, injection DP provides better and more easily account of the shape of the part. Moreover the plasturgist uses more readily a volumic model starting from a direct use of model CAD, the computing times for a DP calculation are definitely higher than those of a PM approach.

3. Example: riveting of the Microturbo part

This is a study of riveting of the external support of rectifier blade in composite injected with short fibers designed by Microturbo (cf. figure 5) with the external metal crown. This problem is related to the industrial need to integrate the composite blades solution in the existing metal unit.

Figure 5: Blade of Microturbo rectifier and local study (external clamp).

The objective of the structural analysis is to give an order of magnitude of the acceptable radial displacement of the boring of the hole of the composite support which undergoes a pressure due to the expansion of the barrel of the rivet during its installation by crushing. It is a local study of the behavior of a subset of the complete structure (the external support of the rectifier blade). To make a mechanical study of the external support, it is essential to know the distribution of local elastic properties.

This distribution cannot be deduced from a distribution of orientation calculated for the support during the injection of the rectifier blade. Consequently, the sequence of the operations leading to the structural analysis of the external support includes the simulation of injection of the rectifier blade (by the Moldflow code in mode DP because of the thickness variations of the paddle) and the modeling of the loading of the boring of the hole of the support external via the juxtaposition of properties between meshes realized by the MTD program (cf. figure 6). The model of injection involves 2344 nodes for 4692 linear triangular elements. The structural analysis of the external clamp is carried out with a mesh of 1367 nodes corresponding to 5501 tetrahedral elements.

Figure 6: Synopsis of the mechanical study (without unit) of the riveting of the blade of Microturbo rectifier, with taking into account of the injection conditions.

CONCLUSION

In the field of the dimensioning of composite structures injected with short fibers, it was until recently impossible to develop a global methodology which includes the link between the jobs of the plasturgist and the mechanical engineer. The heterogeneous nature of the part (distribution and orientation of fibers) depends on the method of manufacture. The tool proposed for integrated dimensioning can contribute to the research of the best ratio cost/performance of the composite parts, while offering to the designer to carry out a loop from the conditions of manufacture through to the mechanical response of a part. The MTD interface is currently being used by the design offices of the industrial partners of the research project, with their own codes of structure.

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